

A METHOD FOR TEMPERATURE MEASUREMENT DURING MMC FABRICATION

Z.Zhang & H.M.Flower

Department of Materials
Imperial College of Science, Technology and Medicine
London SW7 2BP UK.

ABSTRACT

A method has been developed to monitor temperatures at any position in a MMC sample during infiltration by squeeze casting. A purpose designed accessible MMC die assembly, thin and flexible thermocouples and a dedicated computer data logging system are used. The response time of the method is only around 100 milliseconds with sufficient accuracy. The results generated have been successfully used to model heat flow through the fibrous preform. The design features, operation, response time and accuracy of this facility, and an application of the method are described.

Keywords: composites, squeeze casting, process control, temperature measurement

1. INTRODUCTION

Cast fibre reinforced metal matrix composites (MMCs) have attracted great interest from automotive, aerospace and other industries due to their unique combination of properties. Squeeze casting is a well known process for the fabrication of MMCs. This process involves the forced infiltration of a fibrous preform with a molten alloy, with the subsequent solidification of the alloy taking place with the pressure maintained. In order to achieve the maximum potential mechanical properties of the squeeze cast MMCs it is necessary to understand the process of infiltration, solidification and microstructural development. Therefore, as a fundamental study intended for modelling the fabrication process, it is essential to measure the temperature variation at required locations inside and outside the preform during casting.

Previous researchers have often used the measured mould temperature as the preform or MMC sample temperature, and used the temperature of the melt in the crucible to represent the temperature of the melt after pouring and before infiltration. Temperatures obtained in this way are not useful for describing the heat flow in the infiltration process.

There are several difficulties with more direct methods of monitoring the temperature field in MMCs during fabrication. The squeeze casting process takes place in a closed chamber, so that thermocouples are difficult to access in the closed chamber and to locate in any required positions in a preform. The liquid metal infiltration time is only about one second for a preform of 15 mm thickness, therefore, the response of the thermocouples and data logging instrument must be sensitive, fast and accurate enough to accumulate the required data. Since the infiltration process is under high pressure, the thermocouples used must be reliable in this situation. After solidification of

the MMC sample, the thermocouples are embedded in metal and have to be cut out, damaging the thermocouples, so the thermocouples used should be inexpensive.

There is, therefore, a need to develop a method in which all the problems mentioned above can be solved for proper measurement of temperature fields in a MMC during fabrication. This paper describes the method developed by the authors for this purpose.

2. SET UP OF THE METHOD

2.1. The MMC casting facility

The MMC casting facility was designed and constructed to carry out squeeze casting, low pressure casting and vacuum casting in a common die cavity. It consists of an induction furnace for melting alloys, an induction heated die assembly, an ejection mechanism for raising the sample, a 50 ton hydraulic press for squeeze casting, a control system and a computer data logging and processing system. The general description of the facility can be found in reference [1].

2.2. Arrangement of thermocouples

Seven thermocouples are employed to monitor the temperature field during the squeeze casting of a MMC sample. The thermocouple locations are shown in Figure 1. Figure 1 shows that four thermocouples, labelled TC1 to TC4, are located in a preform, the other three thermocouples, labelled TC5 to TC7, are located in significant places in the die. The specially designed ejector (3), with the detachable thermocouple holder (6), makes it possible for thermocouples to be inserted in any position in the preform in the die chamber. For example, as shown in Figure 1, the thermocouple TC1 is located in the centre and top of the preform, to measure the actual melt temperature just before infiltration. TC2, 3 and 4 are located in selected positions in the preform to measure temperatures within the sample. TC5, 6 and 7 are inserted in the die, where they are only 2 mm away from the inside surface of the die, to measure temperatures in the immediate environment of the MMC.

2.3. Preparation of thermocouples

The performance of several types of thermocouples was evaluated in the measurement of temperature in the preform. The response time of commercial metal sheathed thermocouples was too slow, such thermocouples are also too expensive since they can only be used once. Twin bore alumina sheathed thermocouples were not flexible, and fibre insulated thermocouples could be infiltrated by molten metal under high pressure, causing short circuits. Therefore, a special thermocouple was prepared and successfully used for this task.

Figure 2 shows the construction of the thermocouple, which is made with a commercial 0.2 mm diameter nickel-chromium / nickel-aluminium type-K conductor thermocouple cable and copper foil. The wires of the cable are both individually glassfibre insulated, then wrapped and bound together with braided glassfibre. Electric arc welding with Ar gas protection and a tungsten electrode is used to weld the measuring junction, forming a very strong, 0.5 mm diameter small bead junction very close to the insulating glassfibre. The assembly was finally covered in 0.01 mm thick copper foil leaving the junction bare. The overall cross section of the thermocouple is about 1 mm x 1.4 mm.

Experiments have demonstrated the advantages of this form of thermocouple. Accuracy, stability, high thermal electromotive force and low cost are ensured by the selection of K-type thermocouple wires. The small bare measuring junction and the fine diameter of the thermocouple offer a fast response. It is flexible enough to be formed into the required shape. The thin copper foil

sheath prevents melt permeating through the glassfibre insulation under high pressure to cause short circuits, and its small mass has a negligible effect on the surrounding heat field.

2.4. Assembly of the thermocouples

The thermocouples TC1 to TC4, the preform (7) and the detachable holder (6), as shown in Figure 1, are assembled outside the die, then fitted in the ejector (3).

Firstly, a hole is drilled at each required position in the preform (7), then the thermocouple, which is bent into the required shape, is inserted into the hole. After all the wires from the thermocouples have been passed through the hole of the detachable thermocouple holder (6), a paste is used to seal the hole in the holder. After the paste has hardened, the ejector (3) is raised up to the top of the die (5), the holder (6) with the preform (7) and the thermocouples is fitted in the ejector (3), the wires of the thermocouples pass through the central pipe of the ejector (3) and are linked with the data logging terminal. Finally, the ejector (3) is returned to its lowered position.

The preform is pre-heated in the die. After squeeze casting, the ejector is raised up again and the MMC sample and detachable thermocouple holder, with the thermocouples, which are embedded in the MMC sample, are removed together from the ejector. The detachable holder (6) is then removed from the sample, and cleaned for next use.

2.5. Data logging and processing system

An IBM compatible 486-33 computer, a Data Translation 2811-PGL analog and digital I/O board, a DT707-T screw terminal panel equipped with a thermocouple cold-junction compensation circuit, and a colour printer are employed for data collection and treatment. A dedicated computer software package, written in the C programming language, has been developed for this system.

With this system, during operation, up to seven processing parameters can be simultaneously logged on a disk and displayed on the computer monitor with the sampling rate being continuously adjustable from 23 scans per second to 3 scans per minute for each parameter as required. The maximum sampling speed is sufficiently high to study the infiltration process of MMC fabrication. The most important processing parameters, such as the preform temperatures TC1 to TC4 in Figure 1, squeeze pressure and ram speed are logged by the system. The temperatures of TC5 to TC7 are monitored by external digital thermometers.

3. APPLICATION OF THE METHOD

A computer simulation of heat flow during the infiltration of the squeeze casting for the manufacture of MMCs has been devised to describe the transient heat flow during the process[2]. This model is applied to the time for thermal equilibrium between individual fibres and their surrounding metal during the infiltration process.

An experimental data-base has been built up using the method described above to assess the model. Figure 3 shows the comparison of the temperature records measured by different thermocouples and the computed temperature curve of the infiltration process at the location of TC2 in Figure 1. In the experiment, commercial purity aluminium was used as the matrix, and a 100 mm diameter, 15 mm thick Saffil alumina fibre preform with 21% volume fraction fibre and 3 μm fibre diameter was used as the reinforcement. The ram speed was about 0.02 ms^{-1} and the squeeze pressure was 26 MPa. The experimental plot, line 2, which was measured by the specially designed thermocouple, is in agreement with the computer prediction curve line 1, and the difference of the response times between the computed curve line 1 and the measured plot line 2 is less than 0.05 second, as shown in Figure 3, reliably demonstrating the applicability of the model.

4. DISCUSSION

Since the infiltration time in squeeze casting is only in the region of a few seconds, the response time and accuracy of the thermocouples used are extremely important. The question is how can the true temperature of the melt be measured immediately? Actually, the recorded temperature is the temperature of the bead of the thermocouple at that moment.

In the infiltration process, when liquid metal, at temperature T_m , passes the bead of a thermocouple, the bead, initially at a uniform temperature T_i , gains heat from the liquid metal. Because the size of the bead is small and the thermal conductivity of the bead is high, we may consider the temperature gradients within the bead to be negligible.

Of course, the bead of the thermocouple loses some heat by conduction along the thermocouple wires, if the bead is sheathed or coated, longer time is required for the bead to reach the melt temperature T_m , and the temperature of the liquid metal surrounding the bead may be less than T_m due to the heat exchange with the bead when melt passes the bead. In order to take these effects into consideration these three factors are incorporated into the effective bead size, which is effectively increased because the three factors have a similar influence on the temperature of the bead. In the following discussion, all the bead sizes mentioned, such as, volume V , surface area A and radius R refer to the effective size of the thermocouple bead.

For this situation [3], the heat balance at the bead can be written as a simple equation (1):

The rate of heat gain by the bead = The rate of heat transfer from the liquid metal

$$-V\rho C_p \frac{dT}{dt} = hA(T - T_m) \quad (1)$$

Where V = volume of the bead, ρ = mass density of the bead, C_p = heat capacity of the bead at constant pressure, T = temperature, t = time, h = heat transfer coefficient and A = area of the bead exposed to the liquid metal.

Rearranging (1) for integration:

$$\int_{T_i}^T \frac{dT}{T - T_m} = \frac{-hA}{V\rho C_p} \int_0^t dt \quad (2)$$

$$\frac{T - T_m}{T_i - T_m} = \exp\left(\frac{-hAt}{V\rho C_p}\right) \quad (3)$$

$$T = (T_i - T_m) \exp\left(\frac{-hAt}{V\rho C_p}\right) + T_m \quad (4)$$

and from (3)
$$t = \frac{V\rho C_p}{-hA} \ln\left(\frac{T - T_m}{T_i - T_m}\right) \quad (5)$$

Suppose that the bead is a solid ball with radius R

$$V = \frac{4}{3}\pi R^3, \quad A = 4\pi R^2, \quad \frac{A}{V} = \frac{3}{R},$$

therefore (4) becomes

$$T = (T_i - T_m) \exp\left(\frac{-3ht}{R\rho C_p}\right) + T_m \quad (6)$$

1. ejection cylinder, 2. press bed, 3. ejector, 4. support, 5. die, 6. detachable thermocouple holder, 7. preform, 8. liquid metal, 9. induction coil, 10. launder, 11. squeeze ram, 12. thermocouples

Figure 1. Schematic of Squeeze caster and Thermocouple Locations

Figure 2. Construction of the Thermocouple

Line 1 ---- computed prediction curve
 Line 2 ---- specially designed thermocouple with $\phi 0.5$ mm bare bead
 Line 3 ---- thermocouple with $\phi 1.2$ mm bare bead coated with thin refractory slush
 Line 4 ---- commercial $\phi 3$ mm stainless steel sheathed thermocouple

Figure 3. Comparison of Temperature Records Measured by Different Thermocouples and the Computed Curve of the Infiltration Process at the Location of TC2 in Figure 1

and (5) becomes

$$t = R \left(\frac{\rho C_p}{-3h} \right) \ln \left(\frac{T - T_m}{T_i - T_m} \right) \quad (7)$$

Equation (6) shows that for a given bead radius R , the measured temperature T of the bead is only a function of time t . As time t increases the measured temperature T eventually converges with the true temperature T_m . However, in practice, it may be assumed that the true temperature T_m can be represented by the measured temperature T , when T achieves over 99.9% of the T_m . In this case, the time t when the temperature of the bead T reaches the true temperature T_m is in direct proportion with the radius of the bead R , as shown in equation (7). As the radius R decreases, the time t decreases. Ideally, as the radius R tends to zero, the true temperature T_m can be immediately measured. Here the t is a time delay of the measurement of the true temperature T_m , i.e. response time.

The term $(T - T_m)$ in equation (7) is the difference between the measured temperature and the true temperature, in other words, it is the temperature error. If the radius of the bead R is too large, leading to a response time t longer than one second for infiltrating a preform of 15 mm thickness, the measured temperature T will have no chance to converge with the true temperature T_m during the infiltrating process, resulting in an unacceptable error $(T - T_m)$. As shown in Figure 3, the line 4 was recorded by a commercial 3 mm diameter stainless steel sheathed thermocouple, and the line 3 was recorded by a thermocouple with a 1.2 mm diameter bare bead coated with a thin refractory slush, both were recorded under the similar conditions to these of line 2, but both had unacceptably large errors.

Lines 2, 3 and 4 in Figure 3 also clearly show how thermocouples of different size affect the sensitivity of the response time and the accuracy of measurement, and how accurate the special designed thermocouple is. The time delay in line 2 from the initial melt contacting with the bead of the thermocouple to achieving the melt temperature is only about 100 milliseconds. Line 2 is sufficiently accurate to meet the requirement of modelling heat flow in the infiltration process.

5. CONCLUSION

A purpose designed accessible MMC die assembly, thin, flexible, bare bead thermocouples and a computer data logging system are employed for this method of temperature measurement. With the method temperatures at any position in a MMC sample can be monitored during production by squeeze casting. The response time of the thermocouple is only around 100 milliseconds. The temperature recorded is sufficiently accurate, reliable and suited to the modelling of heat flow through the fibrous preform in the infiltration process.

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